

Association of X and P in Classical Physics and Information/Invariance

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In quantum mechanics x and p are considered conjugate variables and d/dx , the generator of translations in x , is an operator representing p (up to the multiplicative factor $-i$). In classical mechanics, however, p is not thought of in terms of the operator d/dx (even though p and x appear in Hamilton's formalism and phase space in statistical mechanics). We argue that the idea of $p \rightarrow (-i) d/dx$ is present in Newtonian mechanics and leads to Fermat's least time principle for light. We try to think in terms of cause and effect and invariance or lack of information.

A key idea we argue is to have a function $f(x=\text{invariant variable})$ with value f_0 at x such that $df/dx = (px)/\text{constant}$. In other words, the generator of translations of an invariant variable x acting on a special function $f(x)$ yields the information describing motion in that direction, namely (px) .

A geometric way to achieve this is with a triangle which is similar to the momentum triangle such that d/dx of the hypotenuse (where x is an invariant variable and d/dx the translation generator) yield $x/\text{hypotenuse}$. This, when multiplied by a constant, creates a conserved quantity, namely momentum in the x direction. From this one may create Fermat's principle of least time for light. Furthermore, one may find another function $A = -Et + (px)x + (py)y + (pz)z$ which behaves in a similar manner i.e. $dA/dx \text{ partial} = (px)$. This is the classical free particle action (both relativistic and nonrelativistic) and the creation of an eigenvalue equation leads to a quantum mechanical form.

Invariance and Information in Newton's First Law

Newton's first law (1) states that a particle at rest (at a specific x) or in uniform motion remains in these states unless acted upon by a force. This suggests a cause-effect relationship and the idea of invariance or a lack of information. In particular, the particle at rest (at a given x) is invariant in time i.e. there is no information about anything special occurring in time so there is no cause and hence no effect. The velocity and momentum remain 0. For the particle moving at uniform speed through space (and in a constant direction) there is invariance in the direction of motion and so no special information about any possible cause so nothing changes.

In the latter case motion through space (in the x direction) may be associated with the mathematical translation generator d/dx . Furthermore both the velocity vector and momentum vector lie in the same direction as the displacement vector. This may seem trivial, but it suggests that both the displacement and momentum/velocity vectors have projections (x, y, z components) such that x/d etc equals $(px)/p$ etc. i.e. one has similar triangles. In Newtonian mechanics one is concerned with $x(t)$ and with p and its changes and so there seems to be no real reason to link a displacement vector with a momentum one or to associate constant momentum in the x direction with d/dx . Nevertheless we have argued that:

Conservation of momentum is equivalent to a spatial invariance in the same direction as dictated by Newton's first law. ((1))

Meaning of x/d , (px/p) In Terms of Changes

Given a vector (x,y,z) it is well known that:

$$d^2 = x^2 + y^2 + z^2 \quad (\text{for a certain metric}) \quad ((2))$$

It is also well-known that projections are given by d multiplied by $\cos(\theta)$, $\sin(\theta)$ etc for a two dimensional vector (x,y) . What is not so commonly stated is that d/dx etc is also directly linked to $\sin(\theta)$.

Consider a two dimensional vector (x,Y) such that Y is a constant. Then:

$$d [d/dx] = x \quad \text{or} \quad d/dx = x/d \quad ((3))$$

x/d is an important form because the displacement vector lies along both the velocity and momentum vectors. Thus a change in d due to x (y constant) yields $x/d = \sin(\theta)$ if angles are measured from the y axis. Multiplying by p , the magnitude of momentum, yields $p x/d = p \sin(\theta) = (px) =$ the x component of momentum. Thus a change in distance (expressed by d/dx acting on d) is equivalent to momentum in that direction. Thus one has the relationship:

$$d/dx \text{ yielding } (px) \text{ if acting upon a "special" function} \quad ((4))$$

This is the operator form used in quantum mechanics, although here it acts on the displacement magnitude i.e. distance. Alternatively it could act on:

$$d/dx (px) x = (px) \quad ((5)) \quad \text{or creating an eigenvalue equation: } -i d/dx \exp(i (px) x) = (px) \exp(i (px) x)$$

Conservation of Momentum and Extremization

We have argued above that $d/dx = x/d = \sin(\theta)$ for $(x,Y=\text{constant})$ for θ measured from the y axis. In addition $(px) = p \sin(\theta)$. From Newton's law, $p(x)$ is constant if there is invariance in x because there is no information at any x i.e. no force(x) which represents information.

This immediately leads to the following scenario. Consider two displacement vectors. The first begins at $(x=0, Y)$ and travels in a straight line to $(x, y=0)$. The second begins at this same point and travels to $(L-x, Y)$. This implies a constraint or information at $y=0$ which changes the y component of both velocity and momentum so that they stop moving in the negative direction and move in the positive. From Newton's first law one would state that a force exists in the y direction, but not in the x .

Next consider an expression which is invariant under shifts of the x origin e.g. $d_1 + d_2$ where $d_1 = \sqrt{(x-0)^2 + Y^2}$ and $d_2 = \sqrt{(L-x)^2 + Y^2}$.

Changing x to $x+dx$, but leaving the starting and ending points unchanged changes d_1 and d_2 , but dx associated with d_1 is linked to $-dx$ for d_2 because L remains constant. Given that $d_1/dx = x/d_1$ and $d_2/dx = -(L-x)/d_2$ i.e. $\sin(\theta_1)$ and $-\sin(\theta_2)$ measured from the y axis together with conservation of momentum in the x direction leads to:

$$(p_1)_x = (p_2)_x \quad \text{or} \quad p \sin(\theta_1) = p \sin(\theta_2) \quad \text{so} \quad p x/d_1 = p (L-x)/d_2 \quad \text{so}$$

$$d_1/dx - d_2/dx = 0 \quad ((6))$$

In other words one has an extremization equation ((6)) for a spatial invariant expression which equates a change due to an invariant spatial variable to the same original projection. The change is expressed by the generator i.e. d/dx if the invariant spatial variable is x .

((6)), however, is the beginning of Fermat's least time principle.

Fermat's Least Time Principle

Consider ((6)) which uses the distance and momentum magnitudes. Given that momentum = mv (nonrelativistically) one may use velocity and momentum interchangeably in ((6)). We argue that ((6)) has the appearance of reflection of light with a flat surfaced mirror existing at $y=0$. Conservation of momentum or velocity in the x direction yields $\sin(\theta_1) = \sin(\theta_2)$ or $\theta_1 = \theta_2$. Thus for reflection with the same index of refraction everywhere one may extremize total distance instead of time.

For refraction, matters are a little different because one deals with light which is governed by $E=pc$. If $c \rightarrow c/n$ then $p \rightarrow pn$ for E to remain constant. Thus the x component of both velocity and momentum cannot be conserved. The momentum component is chosen because there is no source or sink to account for a change in momentum flow in the x direction. Thus instead of extremizing distance, one instead extremizes time = distance/speed. One may also extremize time for reflection, thus one has Fermat's least time principle.

Classical Action

The above ideas for constant speed seem to be based on the following ideas:

(A) There exists a function A such that $d/dx(i) A = b(p_i)$ where $(x_i) = (x, y, z)$ and $(p_x) = (p_x, p_y, p_z)$, where b is a constant so d/dx is associated with (p_x)

(B) If x is invariant (i.e. there is no information in the x direction) then (p_x) should be the same along the x axis. If, for example, there is a change in the y direction at some x_0 ,

then d/dx function (before x_0) = d/dx (function) after x_0 which is an extremization equation equivalent to (px) before = (px) after.

Then conservation of a particular momentum projection means that $dA/dx(i)$ (partial) = (p_i) and $dA_1/dx(i) + dA_2/dx(i) = 0$ where A_2 depends on constant- $x(i)$ to account for the minus sign.

In Fermat's principle this function is $\text{time}(x) = \text{distance}/\text{speed of light}$ where $d/dx = x/d = (px)/p$. Thus there is a close association between x and p for constant motion.

It may be noted that:

$$A = -Et + x(px) + y(py) + z(pz) \text{ works just as well. ((7))}$$

This is the classical action (both relativistic and nonrelativistic) for a free particle with $v=x/t$. Thus A may be used to keep track of conservation of momentum based on the generator d/dx linked to invariance in the spatial direction x . This direction (and y and z) are invariant for free motion. One may use A in an eigenvalue equation i.e.

$$d/dx(i) \text{ partial } \exp(iA) = (p_i) \exp(iA) \text{ ((8))}$$

Information

From Newton's first law, invariance in x means there is no information or force in this direction. Thus momentum in the x direction is conserved i.e. this constant value of momentum governs motion in this direction. One then seeks a special function $f(x)$ such that the translation operator d/dx (applied because of spatial invariance in this direction) brings back the information describing this motion namely (px) .

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that Newton's first law links conservation of momentum (or velocity) to invariance or lack of information in a spatial direction. For example this direction could be x . Movement in x is described by the translation generator d/dx . If one considers a two dimensional problem (x,y) in which there is only invariance (or a lack of information) in the x direction, this means there must be information in the y . For example, there may exist a y force at $y=0$ changing the (py) (y component of momentum) from a negative to a positive value. In such a case one has $(p_1x) = (p_2x)$ i.e. momentum in the x direction does not change. $p_1x = p_1 x/d$ where d is distance from a fixed starting point to the force plane at $y=0$ and p_1 is the magnitude of initial momentum. x/d , however, is equivalent to a d/dx of function, namely $d_1 = \sqrt{xx+YY}$ i.e. distance where $(x=0, Y)$ is the starting point and $(x, 0)$ the ending for the first ray. For fixed starting and ending points one has: $\sin(\theta_1) dx - \sin(\theta_2) dx = 0$, but this is equivalent to $(p_1x) = (p_2x)$ if $p_1 = p_2$. Thus the right angle triangle linked to distance has the same ratios (is similar to) the momentum triangle. Furthermore a change in distance (hypotenuse) in the distance triangle is equal to x/d i.e. $\sin(\theta_1)$ if θ_1 is measured from the y axis. Thus one may equate spatial changes marked by d/dx of an invariant variable with a conserved

quantity. (These ideas may be extended to create Fermat's least time principle for light as discussed in the note.)

They also lead to the idea of d/dx representing the momentum operator. In particular instead of using distance, one may use the function $A = -Et + (px)x + (py)y + (pz)z$ and create an eigenvalue equation e.g. $dA/dx \text{ partial} = (px) \exp(iA)$ as done in quantum mechanics. We argue, however, that the basic ideas for this association are already present in Newtonian mechanics and may be applied to create Fermat's least time principle for light.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Newton%27s_laws_of_motion